

Methods E1

Exclusion criteria:

- (1) Patients who did not return for follow-up, or unwilling to join the study
- (2) Established diagnosis of systemic diseases with altered immunological status, such as congenital immunodeficiency, common variable immunodeficiency, hyper IgE syndrome, autoimmune or autoinflammatory diseases
- (3) Active immune-modulating treatment, including chemotherapy, disease-modifying anti-rheumatic agents (DMARDs), recent systemic steroids (less than 1 month before blood test), systemic calcineurin inhibitor, intravenous immunoglobulin supplement, or anti-B cell therapeutic monoclonal antibodies (rituximab, belimumab) at the time when the blood test was done.

Methods E2

Schematics of patient enrollment and grouping

Table E1

Demographics of milk protein sIgE-sensitized patients.

	CMPA	CMPS	<i>p-value</i>
Basic Characteristics			
Patient number(n)	22	22	
Female, n(%)	7 (31.82)	10(45.45)	0.863
Age (months)(95% C.I.)	23.36(14.16-32.57)	67.59(41.06-94.12)	0.0021**
Laboratory Test (Mean(95% C.I.) / n)			
Serum total IgE (kU/L)	6616.71±3154.83	4297.14±1457.84	0.508
Eosinophils (K/μL)	2.58±1.03/10	0.98±0.44/15	0.118
Symptoms of Milk Allegy (n(%))			
Eczema aggravation	15(68.2)		
Urticaria/Angioedema	8(36.4)		
Respiratory symptoms	1(4.5)		
G.I. symptoms	1(4.5)		
Atopic Diseases (n)			
Atopic dermatitis	17	14	0.322
Allergic rhinitis/conjunctivitis	0	10	0.0005***
Asthma	2	6	0.118
Systemic drug usage			
anti-histamine	4	9	0.099
anti-leukotriene	0	2	0.488

Figure E1

Clinical manifestations of the CMPA group

Figure E2

The correlation between total IgE and milk sIgE of the 44 enrolled patients.

Figure E3

The correlation between milk protein- or component-specific sIgE and sIgG₄ levels, and the age of the patients. The results are shown as Pearson's correlation coefficients. Red shades indicate positive correlations and blue shades suggest the opposite.

Figure E4

Comparison of milk protein/component-specific antibody markers (α -la: α -lactalbumin, β -lg: β -lactoglobulin) in patients presenting with urticaria/angioedema or atopic dermatitis: (A) sIgE/sIgG₄ ratios (B) sIgE levels (C) sIgG₄ levels.

Figure E5

Comparison of milk protein/component-specific antibody markers (α -la: α -lactalbumin, β -lg: β -lactoglobulin) in patients presenting with different symptom severities, incorporating symptom-free group (CMPS) as control.

slgE/slG₄ ratio

slgE

slgG₄

Figure E6

ROC curve analysis of different antibody markers in both study groups (CMPA and CMPS groups), based on a confirmed clinical diagnosis of cow milk protein allergy. The statistical analysis was done using Delong test. Blue dots: slgE/slG4 ratio; maroon triangles: slgE; green squares: slgG₄.

Milk Protein

α-lactalbumin (nBos d 4)

β-lactoglobulin (nBos d 5)

Casein (nBos d 8)

Figure E7

ROC curve analysis of different antibody markers including all 3 groups of participants (CMPA, CMPS and NA groups), based on a confirmed clinical diagnosis of cow milk protein allergy. The statistical analysis was done using Delong test. Blue dots: sIgE/sIgG4 ratio; maroon triangles: sIgE; green squares: sIgG₄. (A) milk protein (B) α-lactalbumin (C) β-lactoglobulin, (D) casein

(A) Milk Protein

(B) α-lactalbumin (nBos d 4)

(C) β-lactoglobulin (nBos d 5)

(D) Casein (nBos d 8)

Table E2

Co-sensitization profile in patients with positive cow-milk sIgE

Allergen	Positive Samples(n) / Tested Samples(n)*			Percentages		
	CMPA	CMPS	Total	CMPA	CMPS	Total
Avocado	3/12	3/11	6/23	25.00%	27.27%	26.09%
Pork	5/12	4/11	9/23	41.67%	36.36%	39.13%
Beef	7/12	5/11	12/23	58.33%	45.45%	52.17%
Cheese	13/14	10/14	23/28	92.86%	71.43%	82.14%
Shrimp	9/18	11/21	20/39	50.00%	52.38%	51.28%
Crab	9/18	10/21	19/39	50.00%	47.62%	48.72%
Clam	9/18	8/20	17/38	50.00%	40.00%	44.74%
Cod	6/15	8/14	14/29	40.00%	57.14%	48.28%
Tuna	8/15	8/15	16/30	53.33%	53.33%	53.33%
Peanut	14/22	12/20	26/42	63.64%	60.00%	61.90%
Soybean	13/17	13/21	26/38	76.47%	61.90%	68.42%
Wheat	10/15	10/14	20/29	66.67%	71.43%	68.97%
Brewer Yeast	6/12	4/11	10/23	50.00%	36.36%	43.48%
Egg yolk	16/19	10/16	26/35	84.21%	62.50%	74.29%
Egg white	18/22	19/21	37/43	81.82%	90.48%	86.05%

* Statistical analysis between CMPA and CMPS groups was done with chi-square test. No statistical significance was found.